

Vaginal Angioleiomyoma - A Single Case Report¹

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Abstract

Leiomyomas are common benign tumors in the uterus. However, vaginal leiomyomas remain an uncommon entity with only a couple hundred reported cases. Here, we report a case of a 43-year-old woman G1P1 who presented with discomfort and feeling of a foreign body in the vagina, difficulty urinating, frequent urination with small portions, and stress urinary incontinence. A physical examination and ultrasonography were performed, and a diagnosis of vaginal fibroid was made. The tumor was removed with a vaginal approach and subsequent histopathology revealed a vaginal leiomyoma.

Keywords

Vaginal Leiomyoma, Angiomatoid Leiomyoma, Leiomyoma, Benign Vaginal Tumor.

Introduction

Vaginal leiomyoma is an extremely rare, benign mesenchymal tumor, with only around 300 reported cases [2]. The vascular form is the rarest type of vaginal leiomyoma, primarily arising from the tunica media layer of veins [8]. While mainly found in the extremities [8], they can also occur in the female reproductive tract, especially in middle-aged women [5]. Vaginal leiomyoma typically develops from the anterior vaginal wall and can present with a range of clinical symptoms [3, 6]. The present report is the first to describe a vascular leiomyoma located between the vaginal wall and the bladder serosa.

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We report a case of a primary vaginal angioleiomyoma originating from the anterior wall, which manifested as lower abdominal pain, discomfort, a sensation of a foreign body in the vagina, difficult and frequent urination, and stress urinary incontinence over 12 months.

Case Report

A 43-year-old female G1P1 presented to the outpatient department with complaints of discomfort and feeling of a foreign body in the vagina, difficult and frequent urination, and stress urinary incontinence for 12 months. Over time, the complaints became more noticeable, and a specialist consulted the patient. A gynecological examination revealed a partially rigid and elastic consistency mass with a smooth surface 80 x 55mm in size in the vagina, which was located in the anterior vaginal wall and was fully covering the urethra. The palpation of the urethra becomes possible after urinary bladder catheterization. The tumor starts 2 cm above the meatus and continues to the anterior fornix. For the differential diagnosis, the patient was consulted by a urologist. The ultrasonography was performed, which showed a 70 x 60 mm hypoechogenic rounded mass with poor inner vascularization, between the anterior wall of the vagina and urethra, mainly on the right side. The mass causes urinary bladder deformation. There was no other abnormality on ultrasonography. The MRI scan findings: A mass with well-defined contours, measuring 5.6 x 4.7 x 6 cm, is identified on the right side of the urethra, containing materials with slight T2 hypointensity and T2 hyperintensity. It compresses and deforms the vaginal lumen in a zigzag pattern, causing dorsal compression of the vagina, its fornix, and anterior lip. The mass appears separate from these structures, cranially covering the bladder. It elevates the posterior wall of the bladder and pulls the urethra to the left, which is wrapped around the mass. Fig. 1 a, b, c. The tumor was surgically removed by vaginal approach without intra and postoperative complications.

Fig.1 a: The MRI scan visualizes a tumor in the anterior wall of the vagina.

Fig. 1 b

Fig.1 c

Fig.2: Intraoperative excision of the tumor

A Foley catheter was introduced in the urinary bladder for urethral protection. The incised mass was then sent for histopathological and immunohistochemical examination with a preoperative diagnosis of vaginal leiomyoma. Fig. 3, 4, 5, 6. The patient was discharged from the hospital on the fourth day of the surgery. The patient was consulted on the tenth day after surgery, and her condition was satisfactory.

Fig.3: CD34, IHC, Zoom x200. Shows multiple blood vessels among the muscle fibers.
CD4 – endotheliocyte or blood vessel marker

Fig.4: H&E, zoom x200. Shows excess muscle fiber (nucleus in blue, stained by hematoxylin. cytoplasm in pink, stained by eosin). It also shows an excess amount of different diameter blood vessels.

Fig.5: Ki67, IHC, zoom x200. It shows a small number of Ki67-positive (proliferating cell nuclear antigen) cells, approximately 4%.

Fig.6: Shows SMA, IHC, zoom x200. It shows a-SMA-positive cells, a smooth muscle cell-specific marker, and an excess of smooth muscle.

Discussion

The majority of leiomyomas in the female reproductive system originate from the uterus and are rarely found in the cervix.

Vagina angioleiomyomas are exceedingly uncommon and are benign mesenchymal tumors that originate from the tunica media of a vein. They commonly arise in the dermis or subcutaneous tissue and represent 5% of all benign soft tissue tumors. They occur most frequently in the superficial fascia of the lower extremities [11, 12, 13].

Vaginal angioleiomyomas are typically seen in females of reproductive age, between 35 and 50 years, with a higher incidence in Caucasian women. [3] Author reports of vaginal angioleiomyoma are incredibly scarce, which contributes to the lack of a typical clinical presentation and makes preoperative diagnosis challenging [7]. These tumors are usually solitary, well-defined, and slow-growing masses, predominantly arising from the anterior vaginal wall [9]. In contrast, malignant tumors are more often found in the posterior vaginal wall, though there are cases of vaginal leiomyomas arising from the posterior or lateral vaginal walls as well. Different from uterine leiomyomas, vaginal lesions are considered as estrogen dependent.

Symptomatology can vary greatly, ranging from being completely asymptomatic for years to presenting with a wide range of signs and symptoms. Depending on the tumor's location and size, symptoms can vary. They may include: lower abdominal pain/ pressure symptoms, low back pain, vaginal discharge/bleeding, dyspareunia, frequency of micturition, dysuria, or other features of urinary obstruction, and protrusion of the mass from the vagina. [1, 2]

Angioleiomyomas situated in the lower portion of the vagina can be mistaken for vaginal cysts or uterine prolapse [10]. The most common misdiagnosis occurs in patients with a leiomyoma presenting as a prolapsed vaginal mass. These individuals often report symptoms such as a protruding vaginal mass,

abdominal pain, and discomfort during defecation and urination. In many cases, the initial diagnosis mistakenly given is 'uterine prolapse,' leading to a delay or inaccuracy in the appropriate treatment. The optimal treatment for vaginal angioleiomyomas is surgical excision through a vaginal approach [4]. To protect the urethra during the procedure, urethral catheterization is advised.

Conclusion

Vaginal leiomyoma is an extremely rare, benign mesenchymal tumor. A patient was admitted at the First University clinic. A physical examination, ultrasonography, and MRI scan were performed, and a diagnosis of vaginal fibroid was made. The tumor was removed with a vaginal approach. The successful surgical excision of the vaginal angioleiomyoma through a vaginal approach, in this case, provides a reassuring demonstration of the effectiveness of this treatment method. Using urethral catheterization during the procedure further ensured the patient's safety. The patient was discharged from the hospital on the fourth day of the surgery. The patient was consulted on the tenth day after surgery, and her condition was satisfactory.

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